

Comparative Study on Strength of Partial RCC Beam by Experimental results and ANSYS Software results

Purushothama C T^a, I R Mithanthaya^b

^a Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Bearys Institute of Technology, Mangalore-574199

^b Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, NMAMIT, Nitte-574110, Karnataka, India

^a puruhassan2017@gmail.com, ^b viceprincipal.nmamit@nitte.edu.in

Abstract – Research on RCC beam by conducting tests is a very tedious job, it requires more materials, labour and time. Hence to reduce this burden best way is go with less experimental tests and more analytical by using software. In this research 4 types of beams of size 150mm x 250mm x 2000mm were casted and tested for 28 days flexural strength. 4 types of beams are M₄₀ concrete throughout the section called conventional beam or reference beam, M₄₀ for top 76mm and M₂₀ for bottom 174mm called partial beam, M₄₀ for top 76mm and M₂₀ for bottom 174mm with 0.5% Industrial Crimped Steel Fibre (ICSF) +0.25% Waste Tyre Steel Fibre (WTSF) called partial beam with fibres & M₄₀ for top 76mm and M₂₀ for bottom 174mm with 0.5% Industrial Crimped Steel Fibre (ICSF) +0.25% Fibre (WTRSF) +20% replacement of cement by fly ash called partial beam with fibre and fly ash. All these beams were analyzed by ANSYS Software by using hardened concrete properties as input data and comparison was done for flexural strength between all 4 types of beams.

Keywords: Conventional RCC beam, Partial RCC beam, Flexure, Industrial Crimped Steel Fibres, Waste Tyre Recycled Steel Fibres, Fly ash, ANSYS.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to IS456-2000 clause 38.1 (d) In Limit state of collapse the tensile strength of concrete is ignored, hence the development of Partial beam. Partial beam is the beam have nominal grade of concrete (Minimum grade of concrete) in tension zone with the idea of saving cement usage. Understanding strength of materials plays a major role in the design of structures to make them economical. In flexural members, understanding compressive strength, tensile strength and shear strength is of prime importance. Flexural members may fail due to either by compression, tension and shear or by combination of tension and shear. In RCC beam design, characteristic of concrete (f_{ck}), yield strength of steel (f_y) and area of tensile steel plays a major role. As per IS456-2000 G-1.1 d) if X_u/d is greater than the limiting value, the section should be redesigned. X_u will divide the beam into two zones, compression and tension. It is a well known fact that, always load will transfer from weak material to strong material, hence concrete in tensile zone will transfer the load to steel, since tensile strength of steel much higher than concrete. Nominal grade of concrete M₂₀ is enough in tensile zone to transfer the force to the steel. Cement used in tensile zone can be reduced either by changing grade of concrete in

tension zone or creating vacuum or using light weight material near neutral axis, this beam can be called as partial RCC beam.

Limit state of collapse for both conventional and partial beams is almost same, but there is a less limit state of serviceability in partial beams since early cracks [1]. Stress varies from top to bottom, maximum at top and bottom, minimum near neutral axis, grade of concrete changed in three layers and found different crack pattern for different combination of grade layers [2]. The grade of concrete changed at different depths from top, the depth of high grade concrete increases in compression zone, enhances initial first crack load [3]. Lightweight materials used near neutral axis, since stress near neutral axis is less. Infilling depth can be calculated by stress block parameters. Concrete can be replaced by infilling material like burnt brick bats to save concrete and to use less cement in construction of beams [4]. Vacuum is created near neutral, where stress is less compared to top and soffit of the beam by placing a waste PVC pipe. Beam was analysed by ANSYS 12.1. It was observed the difference of 5kN in initial crack load and Failure load compare with conventional beam [5]. Concrete, made of fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, cement and water, is a composite material. Steel fiber concrete is popularly used in concrete researches, since it has the capacity to greatly improve some of concrete properties, making the concrete enhance its load carrying capacity, strong impact resistance, and decrease cracks, increase life of structures, etc. In addition, it is also possible to mix steel fiber concrete with nano to form steel fiber nano concrete. In combination with nano, studies of steel fiber concrete have shown that they significantly enhance the tensile strength of steel fiber concrete as well as enhance the ductility of steel fiber concrete if nano [6, 7] is included. Fiber concrete is also used in cracked concrete beams for surface repair. To form a two-layer steel-fiber reinforced concrete beam, this steel fiber concrete layer may be above or below the damaged concrete layer or use both the upper and lower layers of steel-fiber concrete to form three-layer steel fiber reinforced concrete beams, the aim of this repair is to increase the structure's long life. The ANSYS computational simulation and experimental method for the analysis of steel fiber reinforced concrete beams was used in the study [8], with the use of steel fibers in the concrete, the concrete was made to reduce cracking, improve the structure's bearing strength, The initial design parameters such as the effect of the fiber, the effect of the diameter and the number of tensile steel bars, etc. have also been investigated in study [9] and the effect of the concrete grade on beams has not been studied in this study. In a large number of studies, Iskhakov et al. high strength concrete (HSC) on two-layer concrete beams is made of the compressed zone of such a beam section, and the tensile one is made of normal strength concrete (NSC). It is known that the principal disadvantage of HSCs is their low ductility. In order to resolve the problem, fibers are added to the HSC layer. It addresses the effects on structural ductility of different fiber volume ratios. An upper limit of the necessary fiber volume ratio is found based on the compatibility equation of transverse tensile concrete deformations and fiber deformations [10]. Iskhakov's study also examined the steel fiber content in the compressive region of the beam, varying the fiber content and obtaining the required ductility level. Providing sufficient ductility is necessary to design structures for seismic, wind and other dynamic loadings. It has been shown that the content of fibers for such materials, such as reinforcing steel bars for normal RC beams, is important to calculate. The research focuses on finding optimal fiber content, producing as a result the highest Poisson coefficient and higher ductility of the beam section. The fiber weight ratio is used as an option to the fiber volume ratio, as the first is a more efficient parameter for evaluating the fiber content in the concrete mixture. In the context of this study, the experimental results obtained form the basis for general knowledge relating to the formation of two-layer beams [11]. The authors then proceeded to research based on previous studies theoretical studies and tests that showed such beams to be highly efficient, carrying very large bending

moments. The study aims to experimentally verify data relating to the interaction of concrete layers in two-layer beams (TLB) and to demonstrate the efficiency of the two-layer bending element from the beginning of loading to the final stages of loading, including collapse [12]. The research is a further stage of these studies, focused on testing, as in the previous stages, a continuous two-span TLB with optimal steel fiber ratio. This is the first continuous TLB (CTLB) experimental investigation. The study aims to measure the behavior of the CTLB under positive and negative bending moments respectively in the span and above the middle support [13].

2 TYPES OF BEAMS

Fig 2.1

Fig 2.2

Fig 2.3

M40 Top 76mm
M20-Bottom 174mm
 0.5% (ICSF)+0.25(WTSF)
Type-3

Fig 2.4

M40 Top 76mm
M20-Bottom 174mm
 20% Replacement of cement by fly ash at bottom
 0.5% (ICSF)+0.25(WTSF) **Type – 4**

Fig 2.5

Fig 2.1 shows longitudinal section of beam with reinforcement details. Fig 2.2, Fig 2.3, Fig 2.4 and Fig 2.5 shows 4 types of beams.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Fig 3.1

4. FINITE ELEMENT METHOD (FEM)

FEM is a popular method of numerically solving differential equations arising in engineering and mathematical modeling. FEM can be used to solve problems in the areas of interest include the traditional domains of Analysis of structures, heat transfer, fluid flow, mass transport and electromagnetic potential.

The FEM is a general analytical method for solving partial differential functions in two or three space variables. To find a solution to a problem, the FEM subdivides a large system into a smaller system, simpler parts that are called finite elements. This is achieved by a particular space discretization in the space dimensions, which is adopted by the development of a mesh of the body: the numerical domain for the solution, which has a finite number of points. The finite element method formulation of a boundary value problem finally ended in a system of algebraic equations. The Finite Element Method brings solution close to the unknown function over the domain. The simple shape functions that model these finite elements are then assembled into a large system of shape functions that models the entire problem. The FEM then brings a solution close to exact by reducing an associated error function.

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is defined as Studying or analyzing a problem with FEM.

ANSYS

Analysis of Systems (ANSYS) produces and sells finite element analysis software used to solve engineering problems. The software creates simulated mathematical models of structures, electronics, or machine components to simulate strength, toughness, elasticity, temperature distribution, electromagnetism, fluid flow, and other attributes.

Fig 4.1

Fig 4.2

Fig 4.3

Fig 4.4

Figures 4.1 and 4.2 shows ANSYS Modeling

Fig 4.3 is a Solid65 Element for concrete modeling Fig 4.4 is a Beam188 element for reinforcement.

Element types

Concrete: Concrete simulation element: the SOLID65 element, with 8 nodes, this is a 3D element Fig 4.3.

Steel reinforcement: Element of steel bars: used element of beam188: is an element used to model beam reinforcement, used as the basis for Timoshenko beams, consisting of 2 nodes with 6 degrees of freedom at each node Fig 4.4.

Inputs:

1. Density
2. Young's Modulus
3. Poisson's ratio
4. Bulk Modulus
5. Shear Modulus
6. Ultimate tensile strength
7. Ultimate compressive strength

Limitations/Implications: Analysis of beams by ANSYS is focused on conventional beam M_{40} , Partial beam $M_{20} + M_{40}$ and partial beams $M_{20} + M_{40}$ with fibres. In all the beams hardened concrete properties of concrete are used, fibres are not modeled. In all the beams reinforcement provided is same.

5. COMPARISION OF RESULTS

5.1 TYPE1 BEAM: M_{40} concrete throughout the section

EXPERIMENTAL:

Fig 5.1

ANSYS:

Fig 5.2

Table 5.1

LOAD – kN	DEFLECTION – mm EXPERIMENTAL	DEFLECTION – mm ANSYS
0	0	0
10	1.03	1.22
20	1.67	1.89
30	2.31	2.56
40	2.96	3.22
50	3.61	3.69

60	4.30	4.45
70	4.97	5.04
80	6.10	6.33
90	7.37	7.72
100	8.21	8.63
110	-	10.34

Fig 5.3

Discussion: Beam T1 analyzed using ANSYS Software, Load – Deflection results are tabulated. Load –Deflection of beam T1 by Experimental and ANSYS are compared, the results are almost closer and also yielding point in both the results is same, 75kN Fig (5.3).

5.2 TYPE2 BEAM: M_{40} for top 76mm and M_{20} for bottom 174mm.

EXPERIMENTAL:

Type 2 – Beam (T2)

Fig 5.4

ANSYS:

Fig 5.5

Table 5.2

LOAD (kN)	Deflection (mm) Experimental	Deflection (mm) ANSYS
10	1.31	1.43
20	2.16	2.37
30	2.96	3.10
40	3.78	3.94
50	4.61	4.75
60	5.49	5.78
70	7.15	7.41
80	8.18	8.56
90	9.23	9.61
100	10.39	10.95

Fig 5.6

Discussion: Beam T2 analyzed using ANSYS Software, Load – Deflection results are tabulated. Load -Deflection of beam T2 by Experimental and ANSYS are compared, the results are almost closer and also yielding point in both the results is same,60kN and ultimate load 100kN Fig (5.6).

5.3 TYPE3 BEAM: M_{40} for top 76mm and M_{20} for bottom174mm with fibres

EXPERIMENTAL:

Type 3 – Beam (T3)

Fig 5.7

ANSYS:

Fig 5.8

Table 5.3

LOAD (kN)	Deflection (mm) Experimental	Deflection (mm) ANSYS
0	0	0
10	1.3	1.38
20	1.99	2.34
30	2.66	3.19
40	3.39	4.08
50	4.10	4.99
60	4.84	5.88
70	5.74	6.79
80	7.26	8.66
90	8.16	9.85

100	9.08	10.95
105	9.66	12.96

Fig 5.9

Discussion: Beam T3 analyzed using ANSYS Software, Load – Deflection results are tabulated. Load -Deflection of beam T3 by Experimental and ANSYS are compared, the deflection results of experimental are less than ANSYS may be due to fibres, In ANSYS hardened concrete properties of T3 are used as input. But yielding point in both the results is same, 75kN and ultimate load 105kN Fig (5.9).

5.4 TYPE4 BEAM: M_{40} for top 76mm and M_{20} for bottom 174mm with fibres and fly ash.

EXPERIMENTAL:

Type 4 – Beam (T4)

Fig 5.10

ANSYS:

Hardened properties of T4 and T3 are nearly same, only change in fresh properties. T4 is more workable than T3, Class – C fly ash is used in T4. Hence ANSYS results of T3 and T4 are same.

Fig 5.11

Discussion: Load -Deflection of beam T4 by Experimental and ANSYS are compared, the deflection results of experimental are less than ANSYS may be due to use fibres and fly ash. In ANSYS hardened concrete properties of T4 are used as input. But yielding point in both the results is same, 75kN and ultimate load from ANSYS is 105kN and Experimental is 110kN Fig (5.11).

6. CONCLUSION

Following conclusion is made in this research work

- Strength of Partial Beam with fibres and fly ash is little more than the strength of Conventional beam in both yield load and ultimate load.
- Use of less cement in concrete reduces CO₂ emission.
- Use of less cement makes concrete construction economical.
- Use of WTSF (Waste Tyre Steel Fibre) reduces dumping of waste tyres in land filling.
- WTSF can be made effective by twisting or making corrugations, that improves bond with concrete, can reduce use of ICSF (Industrial Tyre Steel Fibre). This saves cost involved in ICSF.
- There is a considerable depth below neutral axis in deep beams; hence more cement can be saved in deep beams.
- Use of class – C fly ash may be the reason for improving first crack load and ultimate load in Beams. Class C fly ash gains strength with ambient temperature and fly ash also improves workability. Workability helps in spreading of steel fibres effectively throughout the mass of concrete and also avoid formation of fibre ball. Increase of workability also helps in compaction and it improves strength of concrete, this may be the reason for high ultimate strength in Beams – T4.
- Saving of cement in Partial Beam – T4 compare with Conventional beam – T1.
 $((438.13 - 394.32)/438.32) \times 100 = 9.995\%$ say 10%

Optimum dosage of fly ash used to replace cement is 20%, since cement used is PPC.

Total cement saved in partial beam is 30%.

- This beam is recommended only for flexural failure.
- FEA is an approximation method. Output is depending discretization and shape of elements. Analysis of beams by ANSYS and experimental are almost nearer, hence experimental results can be accepted.

7. REFERENCES

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